

USE OF VANADOUS SULPHATE AS A REDUCING AGENT. PART IV. ESTIMATION OF TITANIUM.

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Titanium has been estimated potentiometrically by measuring the changes in E. M. F. (against N. C. E.) by titrating with a standard vanadous sulphate solution. The results are satisfactory and the accuracy of the method lies within 2 and 3%. In the presence of iron, three potential breaks are found in the titration curve: the first jump occurs in the reduction of Fe^{+++} to Fe^{++} , the second due to the reaction $V^{++++} + V^{++} = 2V^{+++}$ and the third owing to reaction of Ti^{++++} to Ti^{+++} .

The reaction between vanadous and titanium^{IV} salts does not appear to have been studied by any previous worker. It has been known for a long time that higher salts of vanadium, viz., vanadic acid and vanadyl compounds are reduced by titanous salts.

A method based on these reactions has been described by Kolthoff Furman for the potentiometric estimation of vanadium by titanous salts.

From theoretical consideration as well as from a study of the oxidation potentials of vanadium and titanium salts, it was anticipated that titanium^{IV} salts would be reduced by vanadous salts—a fact which has been verified by actual experiment. The oxidation potentials of the chain V^V to V^{IV} , V^{IV} to V^{III} and V^{III} to V^{II} are -0.2 , $+0.4$ and $+1.2$ volts respectively while that of titanous salts (Ti^{III} to Ti^{IV}) is only 0.04 volt. Hence, titanium salts must be reduced by bivalent vanadium salt and since the oxidation potential of V^{III} to V^{IV} ($+0.4$) is greater than that of Ti^{III} to Ti^{IV} , V^{III} will not be oxidised beyond V^{III} ion. So, the reaction between the two salts takes place according to the equation,

The velocity of the reaction is rather slow at the ordinary temperature and it takes a long time for its completion. The velocity may, however, be increased by a rise in temperature when the reaction goes to completion in a relatively short time. If an excess of vanadous salt be added, the

reaction becomes complete even at the ordinary temperature within a reasonable period of time. Attempts were therefore made to utilise the above reaction for the volumetric estimation of titanium but without any success. This was due to the fact that chemical behaviour of either vanadous or titanous salt towards an indicator showed no difference. No suitable indicator was available which could be used to indicate the end-point. When the Ti salt was reduced with an excess of vanadous salt, the excess could not be estimated by any substance which would preferentially oxidise the V compound without any action upon the titanium salt. So ultimately this method of tackling the problem was abandoned.

Attempts were therefore made to perform the titration potentiometrically by measuring the changes in E. M. F. The results were satisfactory in sulphuric acid solution. If the work is carried out at room temperature, a long time elapses after each addition of reagent before the potential becomes constant. If the titration is made at 70-80° better results are obtained without difficulty. In the region of the end-point the last traces of titanium are reduced slowly so that one must wait a relatively longer time for the potential to become steady. Near the end-point, the titration must be done with slow addition of reagent otherwise an irregular and transient increase in E. M. F. may lead to erroneous results. The accuracy of the method was found to lie within 2-3%.

When the titanium solution contains iron, three potential breaks are found in the titration curve; the first jump occurs in the reduction of Fe^{III} to Fe^{II} ; the second due to the reaction, $\text{V}^{\text{IV}} + \text{V}^{\text{II}} = \text{V}^{\text{III}}$, and the third owing to the reduction of Ti^{IV} to Ti^{III} . It should be noted that during the process of titration of a mixture of iron and titanium, numerically the E. M. F. goes on decreasing, becomes equal to zero and then on interchanging the connections with the potentiometer, it begins to increase. This is due to fact that at the start, $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ solution, which is positive, relative to the normal calomel electrode, is connected with the positive terminal (+E) of the potentiometer and the E. M. F. of the combination is therefore positive. After the reduction of iron and complete conversion of V^{IV} to V^{III} , the solution at once becomes negative to the calomel electrode which is now connected with the positive and the solution with the negative end of the potentiometer so that the E. M. F. of the combination becomes negative. So we may say that during the titration of a mixture of iron and titanium, the E. M. F. (against normal calomel electrode) continually goes on decreasing.

From the equation given above, it is evident that the equivalent weight of vanadous sulphate in the titration of titanium salts is equal to its mole-

cular weight. The strength of the reagent is therefore half the value obtained by standardising against ferric alum or dichromate, provided the salt is purely vanadous and absolutely free from vanadic salt. If the reagent contains some vanadic (V^{VI}) salt the amount of V^{IV} in the solution can be found out in the following way.

Suppose, P c.c. of the mixture containing x c.c. of vanadous (V^{IV}) and y c.c. of vanadic (V^{VI}) solution is equivalent to a c.c. of $0.1N$ ferric alum and b c.c. of $0.1N$ potassium permanganate solution. Then,

$$2x + y = a$$

$$3x + 2y = b$$

whence, $x = 2a - b$. and $y = 2b - 3a$. These values of a and b are found out by titrating with ferric alum and permanganate respectively. Both V^{IV} and V^{VI} are oxidised to V^{V} by ferric salts and to V^{V} by permanganate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pure potassium titanium fluoride (K_2TiF_6) (6.005 g.), twice recrystallised from hot water were dissolved in water and the solution made up

FIG. 1. -

- A—Bridge connecting the N-calomel electrode.
 B—Burette. C—Inlet for CO_2 . D—Exit for CO_2 .
 E—Indicator electrode.
 T—Thermometer.

to 1 litre. An aliquot part of this solution was taken into the titration vessel (Fig. 1) which consists of a 250 c.c. flask closed with a six holed rubber stopper. The end of B passes through the middle hole; platinum electrode passes through another, through a third passes the siphon tube filled with normal potassium chloride and agar agar. Two other openings serve for the entrance and exit of carbon dioxide which is passed through the solution during titration. The thermometer T fills the remaining hole in the stopper. A few c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid were added to the titanium solution which was then diluted with water to make it about $4N$ with respect to sulphuric acid. The solution was heated to about 80° and this temperature was maintained during titration by heating the flask with a micro burner. The end-point was determined from the titration curve (Fig. 2,) and the results of titration are given in Table 1.

TABLE I.

 1 C.c. V^{++} -soln. = 1.366 mg. of Ti. Temperature = 75-80°.

Ti-soln. taken.	H_2SO_4 added.	Total vol.	V-soln. reqd.	Titanium found.	Titanium calc.
25.0 c.c.	10 c.c.	100 c.c.	21.4 c.c.	29.22 mg.	30.06 mg
25.0	10	100	21.6	29.5	
25.0	5	50	22.3	30.46	
25.0	5	50	29.8	29.98	"
10.0	5	50	8.70	11.88	12.024
20.0	10	100	17.25	23.56	24.048

FIG. 2.

Analysis of a Mixture of Iron and Titanium.—25 C.c. of the standard titanium and 10 c.c. of iron alum solution of known strength were introduced into the titration vessel; 5 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid were added and the mixture diluted with water to about 50 c.c. The solution was heated to about 80° and titrated at this temperature with the vanadous

sulphate solution. Fig. 3 shows the titration curve of a mixture containing iron and titanium. Results of analysis are shown in Table II.

FIG. 3.

TABLE II.

1 C.c. of V^{++} -soln. = 1'366 μ g. of Ti and 3'2 mg. of Fe.

V-soln. reqd. by Fe.	Ti.	Iron		Titanium	
		found.	calc.	found.	calc.
16'0 c.c.	21'5 c.c.	51'2 mg.	52'08 mg.	29'36 mg.	30'06 mg.
16'2	21'7	51'84	52'08	29'64	30'06